

ActInf GuestStream 044.1

Tsuchiya & Saigo: Category Theory, Consciousness, Integrated Information

6/13/2023 at 0 UTC, Livestreamed

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FymR0rKdLZo>

Transcript v1, 6/14/2023

00:01 *Hayato*: Hello.

00:04 *Daniel*: Just 1 second. I'll make sure it's going. It's all good. All right, welcome to both. It is June 13 at zero UTC. We're here in active guest stream number 44.1 with Hayato Saigo and Naotsugu Tsuchiya. So we're looking forward to this presentation and discussion. Hayato, please say hello, and then we'll continue with Nasuku's presentation.

00:34 *Hayato*: Hello, I'm Hayato Saigo. I'm a mathematician and a mathematical physicist also interested in consciousness; and have worked a lot with Nao, by using category theory and the application to IIT or other consciousness theories. So, Nao?

00:54 *Nao*: All right. So, my name is Nao Tsuchiya. I'm a professor in Monash University and also having a lab in ATR in Japan. And as a sort of introduction to this today's session, I will give a brief talk on our recent project called the Qualia Structure, which Hayato and I will be collaborating and also a little bit on the Quantum Qualia hypothesis. Both of them are hopefully relevant to active inference issue. So the Qualia Structure project is the Japanese funding that we received recently, and it's going to continue for five years. This will be to establish a super interdisciplinary research program to tackle the problem of consciousness, especially qualia through the interdisciplinary research. We are planning to also host summer school for two to three weeks every year. And here's the fantastic members for this grant. And Hayato is basically working with me in the part of the mathematical approach to the consciousness and qualia. One of the problems, for example, we want to address is, for example, when you see this square, Daniel, what do you see here?

02:26 *Daniel*: Blue.

02:27 *Nao*: Yeah, so you say blue, and I say maybe "ao" in Japanese, and the Haito may say "siniy" in Russian. But we could mean the same experience qualia. But how do we know that we are actually experiencing the same thing? And I'm actually curious whether this kind of question is something that free energy or active inference kind of style approach can ever tackle. And my approach is to go into the category theory kind of inspired direction. And here's the first study that published. We published in a few years ago with Hayato and Shigeru, together with also the another category theorist, Steve Phillips, that in the category theory. There is an interesting lemma called the Yoneda Dilemma that proves that all the relationship characterize its internal intrinsic property. And we are using that idea to study the Qualia. That's the kind of inspiration of our approach. So instead of trying to characterize

what the blue is or red is, we are trying to characterize all the relationship between a particular color or particular qualia to others, exhaustively. And then by finding the correspondence of this relationship, we try to identify what the actual blue is. So if you say blue is similar to green but also similar to red, then that's going to be very different from my blue. And that's the way how we detect this blueness, it's same or different. And one recent application of this kind of idea is this unsupervised alignment that we are using with another collaborator, Masafumi Oizumi in University Tokyo. And I'll skip the detail, but basically what we are doing is to do some kind of experiment and then collect lots of data to obtain so called similarity matrix between all the colors and then without really knowing what color maps onto what we try to use on the relationship to predict what we are seeing. So in a sense, this is a pure category theoretical kind of approach to the problem of consciousness. Then I'll just skip the details here. So we are doing this kind of approach on other types of qualia and then this is the thing that we are planning to do for next five years. And then another just brief kind of introduction. If you have some other question, we can come back later. So this is potentially more to do with an active inference aspect of our approach in a sense. And this is called the Quantum Qualia hypothesis. We published this preprint really recently and so you can access it later. So one of the - there are many programs in the current models of our qualia or consciousness where we tend to think that experience or consciousness is like one point in the high dimensional space. And we use that kind of idea for our previous alignment experiment approach, but it lacks dynamics and it also lacks the effects that we tend to experience where the observation or report or introspection itself sometimes change our qualia, right? And that's sort of the active inference aspect that I'm talking about. Attention or introspection changes experience. But the traditional approach is very difficult to deal with this. And one way to deal with that is this quantum formalism that we think is appropriate. So here we think that there is some kind of qualia experiencing system that is defined as this blue boundary. You can consider that as sort of the Markov blanket-like thing, in the free energy kind of idea. And then we consider particular type of the quale like redness or blueness itself as an observable. It's a terminology in quantum theory. Something that in principle can be observed within this qualia. And then we consider this measurement as a process that probe this qualia observable. And unlike classical theoretical thinking, we think that the measurement or probing of this observable, through, it's called a state, changes its state and also observable itself. And that's something that we can actually formalize mathematically using a concept called, a very general concept, of this conditional probability called instrument. It's very technical for the quick talk, so I'll leave it. But this is a modern quantum theoretical idea that captures both how we can affect on the world and the qualia itself can be affected by that measurement. And then using this we think that we can explain probably qualia in a much more reasonable way with the mathematics mathematical formalism, and so far, it's just a kind of theory, but we already think that it's probably better than the existing kind of a model of, for example, attention and the consciousness. And also it also provides some kind of prediction and the explanation of why some of the two concepts or two experience can feel different depending on the order that you experience. So this is just like conceptual kind of example. But if I ask you, Daniel, that is China similar to North Korea? Then you might say probably no, right?

09:11 *Daniel*: I don't even know the reference point.

09:14 *Nao*: Yeah, okay. But let's say just subjectively, China doesn't feel similar to North Korea.

09:19 *Daniel*: Okay.

09:20 *Nao*: Yeah. However, if I reverse the order, is now North Korea similar to China, then many people actually start to say that, yeah, it's kind of similar.

09:36 *Daniel*: Does that have to do with one being larger or what? Is it about the order that primes people to respond differently?

09:44 *Nao*: Yeah, so many people have already came up with many different kind of ideas to explain this kind of individual aspects of this order effect. But as we mentioned, we are actually computing or measuring these kind of order effects systematically through all combination of the colors, for example. Then it's hard to systematically explain why this order effect emerges in one case but not the other, and in which direction. Right, but that's what we found, basically. And but using this in a quantum cognition kind of framework, we can explain it really nicely. In this case, it's just a projection postulate, but we are probably going to extend much more in the more instrument-like framework in the future. Yeah. And also we are also predicting that there may be some kind of, violation of Bell's inequality in perception. And if we can confirm that, that also gives a credence to our proposal that the qualia needs to be framed or explained in the quantum framework. So I think that's probably enough to start up the conversation, I guess.

11:13 *Daniel*: Awesome. Okay, great. Lot to jump into. I'll... Share my screen so we can take some notes. Okay. Hayato, do you want to give a first remark or I'm happy to, but do you have a first remark or what parts of the work do you want to reflect on first?

11:53 *Hayato*: I think maybe the Categorical approach -- the importance of Categorical approach is one issue to talk with you, I think, because you first pointed out that paper with Tsuchiya in 2016. So I'm interested in why you and your colleagues are interested in that paper from the active inference side. So can you explain some feeling?

12:35 *Daniel*: Yes. So this is using category theory to assess the relationship between consciousness and integrated information theory with the two of you and Taguchi from 2016. So I've long been interested in scale-free or scale-independent ways to describe systems and information theory has been recognized as one of those approaches. And information theory has been proposed to not just play, of course, a central role in the functionality of information systems, but with IIT and related theorems, to also strike at the heart of the most quintessential aspect of our conscious experience. So that seems like an incredible synthesis of the functionality of systems that don't necessarily seem to have anything qualia-like at all, merely performing calculations, like a super fast abacus basically. And so I am curious and feel free to address either of these things. When we describe information systems, what is it that would or could or is experienced? Are they experiencing their information, what they are processing or what is it about information integration that would grant a system the ability to move beyond a behavioral functionality into, again, strike at the heart of one of the most ineffable questions that the mind can really consider.

14:41 *Hayato*: Okay, interesting actually the category itself in mathematics originated created in mid 20th century to bridge the two different fields, that is geometry and algebra, more specifically the topology. You know something about topology maybe, which is a very general kind of mathematical

mesos to capture the essence of the figures like a circle or complicated figures. And the fundamental problem of the topology is: can you identify the two different figures? Essentially that means, can you transform continuously to the other figures or not? So if the one figure goes to another figure with a continuous transformation and back then it is viewed as essentially the same. But to determine the two figures as the same is a very difficult question. So like great mathematician Poincaré figured out the utility of the algebraic method that like making the one figure to the other from the figure you can construct the algebra system like groups or something and then the transform the problem into the algebra region. Then the point is, very essential point, is taking one figure to constructing one algebra from the one figure is not sufficient. The point is the relation should be transformed the other regions. So one region here, other regions here but one to one correspondence of object is not sufficient. But the relations if you can transform the order relations into the other regions, then you can prove something from one region to another region. Because this is a notion of the function like the region intuitively I talked about using term the region. It is mathematically called category. Category consists of objects and arrows, arrows or morphism which is a generate kind of relationship between these objects. So a topological region is some kind of category of topology like a top that projects topological space and continuous functions, continuous mapping is arrow or something. There are other regions, for example algebraic regions like groups and group homomorphism or the module vector space or something. So something algebraic and the relationship between them. So category is defined to formulate the intuitive concept of bridging something -- functor. So first [?names?] defined category to define this notion of functor by the bridging to region. Then, if this is established, then you can infer about the topological region category by using the algebraic relation or something. So we that is Nao, Shigeru, and me talked about the possible application of this kind of argument into the consciousness study -- it is just a program of bridging different kind of regions like physically testable region and our role, experience itself or something. So it is qualia, it seems qualia it is too difficult question too hard problem to connect to these regions if you only focus on the object. But the relationship, if you can compare the relationship then you can infer something about you cannot directly touch or you directly manipulate. So this is the idea.

19:47 *Nao*: Maybe I'll just add a little bit. As Hayato said, you are taking really diligent notes. So that may be quite good But from my end -- So this paper was inspired by really talking to Hayato Shigaru and the meeting in this summer school on consciousness. And there I encountered in this category theory for the first time. And there were several shocking concepts that I learned from this first encounter. One is that there is a way to compare two completely different things and then extract common structure between them. And Hayato first introduced me this very strange paper which I didn't understand at all, but was so interesting that I could read for hours and hours. It's called the "Rosetta Stone". It points out commonality between the topology, quantum physics, logic, and computation. That was the title. And then I didn't understand what the heck is this in a paper, but that uses this category theory. And as a whole, I feel like I see. So maybe if we understand the structure behind each of this concrete example, we may be able to find a commonality or explanation at that level. And that naturally applied to my program at the time, which is how to bridge the gap between the qualia and the information structure derived from neural activity. This looks also completely different. But if there is any possibility to bridge the gap, it must be some kind of structural mathematics, and that is category theory.

21:58 *Hayato*: One other point is, that I think you can get the ideas of functors by bridging the two regions. Then the really interesting thing, another really interesting concept is called natural transformation. Natural transformation is the kind of deformation or transformation between transformations. So you imagine some theory bridge some region to the another region. So there is one meta level arrow, but another theory predicts another thing or something. But can you connect these theories or models? This is a problem of natural transformation. So one representation, one theory or something may map the one region to another region but there may be another, various kind of mappings functors so the problem is to compare or to unite to connect this transformation function is called natural transformation. If the functor is naturally isomorphic, that means there is a reversible natural transformation between functors. Then these theories seems different but essentially same. So kind of natural transformation is maybe the hint to connect the various theories on consciousness or something. And also our consciousness experience itself will be connected to the concept of natural transformation. Because I see something that the different thing, something, but there is no divided discrete kind of structure, but there is some continuous or relating something. So this is this view is something like functor. Another view is something like functor, but there is no division. There is some relationship. So our experience maybe itself a kind of product of a natural transformation. Like, maybe Nao you can explain, like a periphery. Or maybe Nao, you are muted, muted.

24:49 *Nao*: Is it all right if I draw some kind of figure?

24:52 *Daniel*: Of course. Would you like to share your screen?

24:55 *Hayato*: Yeah.

24:55 *Nao*: And also if you can give me the access to the annotation okay.

25:03 *Daniel*: I will make it so everyone can edit and I'll put it into the chat here. And then also if you want to draw, that would be awesome.

25:14 *Hayato*: Yeah.

25:15 *Nao*: Do you see the whiteboard now?

25:17 *Daniel*: Looks good.

25:18 *Hayato*: Yeah.

25:19 *Nao*: So just to kind of recap, what Hayato was talking about is that we tend to think about something like a category, and then another category is there. And then there is some kind of object which could be quite abstract. And then it's related by arrow like this. And then if this category C is somehow possible to map onto this category D while kind of preserving this arrow. For example, this arrow goes to here, and then this arrow goes to here. And then each object is also preserved. Then it's much more than the usual kind of idea of a function between the sets. Right. Because it also impose the correspondence between the relationship. And in our idea, basically, if this is, let's say, qualia of the category, and if this is a neuronal activity or maybe information domain, and then maybe we can have a back and forth of the functor, that would be great. Usually most of the mathematical theory of consciousness tries to go from here to here, right? Let's say in the case of IIT - arrow here. And then what Hayato was kind of talking in a way as natural transformation, is this kind of secondary level

arrow. Let's say. I don't know whether free energy or active inference can count as a prediction from neural activity to the particular qualia, but let's say if there is something like that, and then maybe there is some kind of a translation between these two theories. Yeah. If that exists, that's called a natural transformation.

27:30 *Daniel*: Awesome. A few comments on this. The idea of mapping the maps between the spaces is so important. It reminds me of metaphor where we're conveying relationships and saying, well, it's like a hammer, or it is a hammer. For this other situation. So that's how we get few shot learning and applicability and how we grasp concepts, is perhaps developmentally or from an evolutionary perspective, in a large extent by generalizing our spatial and embodied understandings. And then certainly communication! If you want to have some semantics that are being communicated across minds, through an interface, through a classical interface, then certainly you want the structure to be preserved. And then I think the one that you have here is one of the most provocative for those empirically studying consciousness because it's kind of like, this side is empirical and let's just say we don't know what the Q side is for now, but let's just say it's another space that isn't that. And then if there is a certain landscape that neural activity patterns flow through like some kind of winnerless competition or you get some sort of limit cycle and you find that there's a limit cycle of neural activity and then there's also -- that is being paralleled by experiential cycles, then that is not just an accounting system. That's a very strong finding about potentially the real underlying causal system, especially because it can suggest unique other explanations or manipulations to make.

29:28 *Nao*: Right. Do you want to mention anything about the metaphor?

29:32 *Hayato*: Yeah, before that, very hard to say. The technical remark is that for the original problem that connects topology and algebra, then in that case the algebra is more concrete, more manipulative in that case. And the topology is something mysterious in this case. So in general the functor is a kind of generalization of mapping in sets. So there's something mysterious, into something concrete. So Nao's picture C and D should be switched maybe in that case. But of course there is a back and maybe, back and forth. So the idea is your blue and my blue program is for example, you can prove that your blue and my blue is different. If there's something, informational or something, the detectable structure is completely different, then your blue and my blue is different. Of course you cannot prove the sameness between your blue and my blue if there is no, how to say, the back and forth functor. But even if you don't have the backwards functor, at least you can demonstrate that your blue and my blue is different, seems to be different if the correspondence is functorial or something. So it is a big step from the experience side, and me and colleagues do such a thing. So this is not by focusing your blue, my blue only, but your blue red something or you don't have to say, even do not have to say the name of something. So just, how to say, no labeling for example, but the relationship you can teach the relationship these things. You can teach the relationship these things. So then compare that. So very interestingly, in general the structure is surprisingly coherent between persons. It is very nice and also maybe it's suggesting that the known isomorphic case, then your blue and my blue is something different or something. So I think this approach is very interesting even if there's no bidirectionality or only one direction, but even that case it is useful. Yeah, it is my remark.

32:57 *Daniel*: Yeah, please. And then I'll have a question about your drawing.

33:01 *Nao*: Right. So this is one of the slides that I didn't show today. But what Hayato was talking about is kind of explaining this figure. Like the way you experience red is related to with the other experience, not only color but shape and also sound and so on in a very complicated way. And then we can actually measure how similar they are by asking the people and then you can also do that for the other people. And then these two similarity metrics can be directly compared with our new method of this unsupervised learning. And also IIT, for example, may allow us in the future to go back and forth between this qualia structure and the information structure. Mathematically, we believe that the information structure to information structure should be potentially translatable in some way. And if that is possible in some way, eventually we may be able to say: ah, okay, so the way you are experienced red is same or different in this way or that way. That's sort of the idea.

34:18 *Daniel*: Can you go back to your drawing?

34:21 *Nao*: Right.

34:26 *Daniel*: Awesome. So for the top arrow, if we're kind of just exploring, what might it mean that IIT is going back and forth and also that active inference is going back and forth. So what exactly does the edge between C and D represent in IIT? Is that a quantitative evaluation like the Phi variable, or what is being accounted for with that arrow?

35:00 *Nao*: Do you want to say something?

35:01 *Hayato*: Yeah. There is various possibilities actually. For example, the sameness or difference. So if you have some kind of gradation with sameness, yeah, sameness gradation. But to formulate the gradation of sameness, you have to move on the enriched category. Not a simple kind of category, but it's a generalized kind of category called enriched category. In that case, for example, the simplest example for enriched category is generalized metric space. In metric space, for example, the point P and P itself has a distance zero of course, and kind of P to Q, Q to R is there is a triangular inequality or something. Then it can be considered as a generalized kind of compositional structure called enriched category. It is a typical kind of enriched category, but symmetry does not always hold or something. So this is one, how to say, one small step to grasp our Qualia structure. Because like Nao pointed out, North Korea - China distance and the China - North Korea distance is in general different or something. So almost all studies assume that some symmetry, but we need to go beyond that. And then maybe the one number or something is too poor to represent everything. So you have to go more and more richer structure, like not just numbers but some kind of projection operator or something. Then you enter into the quantum region. So relationship we feel should be maybe should be represented from some kind of relationship between the notion of state in quantum theory and the state transition between that. So our approach is step by step and you can choose the many arrows to study something and then goes to unify the more and more general kind of arrows and categories. And this is just for the speculation but this kind of quantum theoretical like as a mathematical framework do not need to the kind of physics but the kind of mathematics can you use unify these kind things.

38:30 *Daniel*: Awesome, just a few comments on that. When we're doing free energy minimization, we use the KL divergence which is very importantly not a distance because a distance would have the symmetry characteristic. And so the KL is chosen because it's easy to fit optimization on these variational distributions, but it's almost like it's a feature, not a bug, that the KL divergence between Q

and P is not the same as P and Q , because it turns out that that kind of a divergence-based quantification actually has some advantages over a distance measure. And then the mapping between observables and hidden states and the cognitive operators that we bring to bear on that kind of mapping problem -- Those are some of the most fundamental pieces of the partially observable Markov decision processes that are used in the active inference generative model, which is: first the mapping between observables and hidden states, and then how do hidden states change through time and how does action selection, policy selection influence how hidden states unfold through time? So this mapping between hidden states and observables and between hidden states and the hidden state at the next time point, and again how action influences that -- if you understand those operations, then it's like a game of chess and the ball just rolls downhill and the variational distribution works exceedingly well. But when those are off base, then you're fitting your way like right off a cliff.

40:34 *Nao*: So maybe then I'll just add one more point. So you asked in the original like five minutes ago what each of these points or arrow correspond to in the case of the IIT and so on. And then this is kind of related to all these ideas. But one of the fundamental insights from IIT but also from philosophy, especially some kind of philosophy called the process theory -- it is important to really understand that the process of flow or movement is really fundamentally important kind of aspect of things. And then that may be really distinguishing some kind of static sets, or the thing in the static world. When they start to interact, and when the process emerge, then something starts to potentially generate or support subjective quality like qualia kind of thing. And in the case of the IIT, it is deeply kind of entrenched in this formation of the transition probability matrix of an entity like how this thing, neuron or logic gate, it might have come from the previous state and it may go into the next state. So any kind of a moment is already embedding the possible previous and the possible future. There is some kind of a widths in the moment because it's a process. And when the process is considered, then as I have said, that this kind of dot is a very kind of two-thing kind of structure to think about. So we need a more elaborated structure of a dot itself. But the category theory is great in the sense that each dot can itself contain complicated structure. It's just represented as a single dot but it can contain something more. So in an upshot, one dot could correspond to a collection of the neuronal states and the connectivity pattern and things like that, which can go from one to the other. And then this kind of movement may correspond to something like we see redness or whatever in this way - but that's also with respect to other kind of arrows as well. And that's the sort of way of the relationship that we are trying to characterize both in the domain but qualia, but also brain is also the way of the relationship, gigantic ones, right? And as you said, that transition from one state to the another state that's pretty much like dynamical system-like approach and then the simple idea called a monoid is applicable to this kind of dynamical system approach. Correct me Hayato, if I'm saying something out of the bounds of my comfort zone, but any kind of state can transition into another state and then this transition itself can be represented by the arrow. The combination of that particular kind of arrow composition may correspond to one experience. So that's one thing I wanted to say. The other thing that I had also mentioned about observable state and why we are interested in a quantum framework, quantum theory, by the way, it's not a quantum brain hypothesis. We are not saying that quantum phenomena in the brain is critical for consciousness, but it's just a mathematical structure of the quantum theory that is important to understand the qualia. And the essence is most likely to be this noncommutativity. Any kind of process that you do, like cooking, putting the water, and then muddle, is different from muddle

and then putting water. Right? And so any kind of process we do, there is some kind of temporal dependency that commutativity doesn't hold and that's also probably the case for the qualia. And if that's the case, then for you maybe it's a bit surprising, but Bayesian kind of statistics and Bayesian probability may not work as you might wish.

45:44 *Hayato*: Yes. So in other words, using the Quantum mathematics there is a quite good generalization of Bayesian innovation, or Bayesian kind of inference. Yes, actually the one step generalization is called a projection in kind of mathematics. Then there is more generalization called "instrument". So instrument is general notion of measurements like a system and environment interacting. Then more precisely, the measurement is something like the interaction feature has some probe of the apparatus. So probe is some kind of the apparatus is some very small tips or something which can be considered as a quantum, that this quantum system and this probe system interacting quantumly, then we can measure this probe by the macro side of the apparatus. So this is a very general kind of measurement which is identified mathematically with the notion of instrument originated by the Davis and Lewis and Ozawa, one of our collaborators. We begin in the collaboration, but Ozawa, who is also famous for the Ozawa's inequality, Ozawa inequality as a generalization of Heisenberg's Inequality, a valid version of Heisenberg Onequality. But he identified this general notion measurement and instrument called a completely positive instrument in mathematics. But this CP completely positive instrument is quite general and generalizing very beautifully the Bayesian inference into the quantum side. So I think using, focusing this kind of instrument kind of concept, is the key maybe to bridge the active inference side on our side and quantum side or something. So, yeah, it is my speculation, but I think it is very fruitful direction.

48:45 *Daniel*: It's awesome. Just one comment on that. The probe with the instrument or the quantum reference frame, I believe, as Chris Fields might describe it, is an experimenter's choice. And so the way that we could talk about policy selection and inference on which experiment to run would be in terms of which sequence of observations is going to minimize expected free energy. So which sequence of observations is going to have high pragmatic value and epistemic value -- that's the expected free energy functional. Now, as researchers, we might seek out the most informative experiments and not prefer to see a certain measurement. So we can say, well, all measurements are a priori equally pragmatically valuable to us. So now expected free energy is going to be driven by information maximization, just by pure learning. But this recognition that action is woven into the process of reducing uncertainty about other systems across blankets. It's absolutely fundamental, because if you don't have the constraint that you need to actively select which experiments to run and to probe and to interfere in this quantum way, this way described by quantum mathematics, you're kind of in a delusional alternative world where you get information from photons, but you don't have a sensor. So it's not an empirically tractable world unless we take on this constraint. And then once we do, our mathematics are the quantum mathematics. And again, it's kind of a subtle point. This isn't the Orch-OR or this isn't necessarily taking a stance one way or the other on what kinds of electronic scale quantum phenomena exist in any system, but rather just sees quantum mathematics as fundamental to decision making and uncertainty, which is quite a change from how it's been discussed for 100 years.

51:11 *Hayato*: Actually, as Nao said, we are not dependent on the hypothesis. Like there is a quantum physical process behind the qualia. But why we can use the quantum mathematic is very simple reason.

Because conventional probability theory, classical probability theory depend on the probability space. Classical one is too narrow to capture, for example, order effect or something. But you can generalize it. So quantum mathematics is just generalized the classical mathematics. And I believe that why quantum mathematics is found for quantum physics is a very simple reason because in classical physics, some kind of determinism. Classical Determinism is very universal and the probability only comes from some kind of ignorance of us. But in quantum physical context there is some kind of very fundamental randomness. The fundamental accidents or something is found and they are all surprised because if you go into the microsite, the determinism should be stronger and stronger they sold. But actually there needs some kind, they found fundamental noncommutativity and microside. For example Bohr and Heisenberg, some people pointed out that even Classical, or even sorry, on the macroscopic side. But this kind of the importance of noncommutativity is very universal, not especially in microsite, but it is a historical reason that we first find in mathematics in the microsite. But there is many, many phenomena which cannot be captured by the determinism or the classical probability theory. So I think the qualia or something is just some kind of.

53:57 *Nao*: Example.

53:58 *Hayato*: Yeah, example, yes.

54:00 *Nao*: By the way, maybe Daniel, can you replace this quantum consciousness with the quantum qualia?

54:07 *Daniel*: Yes.

54:07 *Nao*: So the quantum consciousness has been used to imply this quantum brain hypothesis, which may be potentially true, but so far we don't really see the strong evidence about this particular thing.

54:33 *Daniel*: What's funny, I'm thinking of the classic qualia question what is it like to be a bat? And it's like, what if the like is interpreted as a metaphor? What if there's a metaphorical mapping to bat which is an observer dependent mapping amongst spaces? Because we've moved the focus from the objective standalone experience of the bat to considering mappings amongst cognitive systems -- one critical, one being, for example, whoever's listening to the question and a bat who's the one who actually answers that question.

55:31 *Nao*: Okay, so you asked also about the inspiration from the category theory relevant to the issue of the metaphor, right? And also communication. Now, it's a bit far from this quantum qualia and they jump back to another topic. Metaphor is something that the Hayato has been working on. So yeah, but the other part, which is this communication. And that's something that we also wrote together last year and using this concept called adjunction in category theory, which may be also interesting to discuss. So in 2016 paper we already mentioned that category theory is very promising for the study of consciousness precisely because it provides different levels of sameness. When I heard this from Hayato, I was like what do you mean!? But as simultaneously it makes a lot of sense and in fact many controversy or confusion among the field of consciousness, but not only for consciousness, other fields like ecology as well, like classification of the animal species and things like that all depends on this. What do you mean by the same? Right? And this is something that also relates to what you are talking

about a moment ago, which is observer dependence, right? Even at the very bottom of this reality, I think that what matters is some notion of this subjective choice of what it means to be the same. Equivalence or adjunction is a particularly interesting kind of situation where, for example, integer and the real number is definitely different. But in terms of the relationship, if you start to think about the relationship, there is some kind of one to one correspondence between them. And also Hayato's book, also written in Japanese, but recently I did read it and one of the interesting example is also multiplication and exponentiation at the level of object or number it doesn't match, right? But there is a very nice relationship between them that is very fundamental and something like this apparently completely different thing but finding really meaningful relationship that's very fundamental. In communication, we are talking different kind of language with different kind of meaning, but because when I say something, you reply and then there is some kind of systematic difference between what I expect and what I hear. That's the kind of prediction error, right? I think the prediction error may not need to be minimized in fact, but as long as it's consistent and systematic then it actually works as a very nice translational kind of device. After living like 20 years, more than 20 years of living outside of Japan, I still have very strong English accent, either in Japanese or Japanese, living in Australia or US. I can't minimize this prediction error. But because I have this systematic prediction error for you, you totally understand me, right? Something like this is the interesting thing about adjunction.

59:47 *Daniel*: This makes me think about nested reference frames in communication. And let's just say that the expected free energy or maybe even the integrated information content is such and such a level, but it varies within some range. It's 100 plus or minus ten. Instead of just trying to naively minimize that to zero, we can create a nested model such that we expect that to be 100 plus or minus ten, at which point the non zero value is stabilized or buffered. And so then that becomes the kind of, stabilizes or wraps the fact that we're not perfectly transmitting information but we can be perfectly aligned, that we're not perfectly transmitting information. And also our language understanding, for fluent speakers, we're able to map the phonemes a little bit deeper. We're able to read between the lines or listen between the phonemes. So that people who say words differently map to the exact same syntax, let alone the semantics. The sound gets kind of abstracted out, but it influences our qualia. So something is being passed forward with tonality and the timing. And I wonder about with of course large language models how much context they're able to garner from the string of tokens when for our experience, sending and receiving natural language communication, it's all about the timing and the tone and the setting. And so finding ways that we can describe that type of information, the category theory capacity for the different levels of sameness, seems like exactly the tool that we need.

1:02:18 *Nao*: Do you want to add anything?

1:02:20 *Hayato*: Yeah, I'm thinking about but.

1:02:25 *Nao*: About the multilevel kind of free energy minima. I actually have a question to you actually. So I recently discussed with roboticist in Japan, Jun Tani, do you know his work? He is using this predictive coding kind of scheme for constructing the set of autonomous robot and he thinks this intermingle of the top-down prediction and the bottom-up prediction error is the place that Qualia emerges and things like that. But one of his most interesting aspect of his model to me is that he has this different timescale for his neural system. The most peripheral motor level and sensory level has a very fast time scale. So that tries to match with what's happening outside and then what they want to do

towards outside. And the intermediate level has a slightly longer kind of time scale. So there is some kind of inertia and an even higher level has a much much longer timescale. In the probably neural system there is also different level of the timescale and also different levels of the mechanism acting at the same time like change in the activity state in spiking or not and also release of the synaptic neurotransmitters that could increase or decrease over the time and also even the new neurons emerging and going out. So - the minimization, when you are talking about minimization, probably that kind of minimization is actually happening independently and also coherently potentially or contradictory across different levels and also regions. And there may be some kind of effort or whatever to also coordinate these kind of contradictory demands of the minimization. What do you think about this issue? Do you still think it's a useful way to think about or use the term minimization in this situation?

1:05:01 *Daniel*: That's a great question. Well, one thing that stood out to me was you described the slower moving levels as having inertia and from the Bayesian mechanics perspective that's exactly how we would model it. They're slower moving, they have more inertia, and they move more like classical objects, whereas the faster timescales are moving more like lighter particles, more like that quantum probe in the limit, and then the sort of center or the highest nested model would be like the most cognitively massive, potentially the slowest, potentially integrating information over the longest time window. And certainly this is underlain by these multiple timescales of mechanism spiking neurons from a few hundred milliseconds timescale, neuromodulatory processes over seconds and minutes, synaptic plasticity even neurogenesis and the development of our brain. So what does it really mean that minimization is occurring when we have this heterarchy where we have similar types of free energy minimizing units or active inference units within a level like cortical columns or grid cell units, and then also we have these nested models that are optimizing across spatial temporarily separated scales. Well, one paper that looked at this was Our Livestream 42 on the SLAM, simultaneous localization and mapping, also in robotics. And so they had a two nested model with two steps and the lower level was like the tactics and that was where you had the motor and the sensors, and then the nested model was slower that was like where do I want to be?, that was more like the strategy And you can create an expected free energy functional that sums across those two levels. How you tune the parameters is going to matter because - this comes up with preference learning. If you have left or turn and right turn and your preference vector is like two and one versus 2 million and 1 million, then the ratio of the preference is the same, but the amplitude of the preference is a lot different, which is going to swing the model towards valuing pragmatic outcomes. Whereas if you had 0.2 and 0.1, the ratio of the preference would still be the same, but it's such a small amplitude preference. And so similarly, with expected free energy minimization you could make it so that the joint minimization was driven by just the top level of the model. And then the sort of contradictions or even increases in expected free energy of the lower sensory model would basically always be accepted in service of the top model or vice versa. And it seems like biological systems with their sort of precarious or self organized criticality operations, they're poised where you can have propagations where small changes in the bottom up model can propagate and induce phase changes of higher levels and vice versa. So they're certainly poised parametrically at a special place where the composition of the faster sensory motor models and the slower like cognitive or narrative or metacognitive levels it's all poised in a very integrated way, potentially even one that is where the IIT measures tell us something useful. But yes, the contradictory demands of subunits within a level of collective behavior and across levels -- as a biologist I think we

just point to ecology, evolution and development and just distributed systems that don't exist at an adaptive point or implement adaptive dynamics amidst uncertainty, they just fail to exist. And so the complex biological systems that we observe today do manage that trade off. And then in robotics, they have this unique challenge of developing systems with one shot or with iterated development that do have some of those properties. But for sure, there's no reason to think that just by laying out a nested active inference model that you would actually get, like, a more adaptive decision making agent. In fact, as you nest models, the state space of these models becomes vast. And with some back of the envelope calculations, you can see, like, well, if I do this level of nesting and have this kind of sensor array, we need this absurd amount of data to actually parameterize this model. And by the time we collected that many observations, maybe the causal structure that we learned to the world, 200 hours of video ago don't apply.

1:11:03 *Nao*: Yeah, that could be quite a huge difference between probably IIT and free energy. I think the IIT explicitly states that this time scale that matters, but in this case, it's just about qualia is a particular time scale that maximize integrated information and that corresponds to the timescale of our experience. In Tani's model, the slowest timescale is like, on the order of 100 milliseconds or something like that. And also new synaptic plasticity is on the order of hours. And most likely spiking neurons seems to be more mattering with respect to our particular experience at each moment. Right. And why it is the case that the provisional answer provided by IIT is that because at that particular time scale, integrated information is maximized, across the scale and across the regions. But this is a huge conjecture, and nobody knows whether this is true or not. And when we use the Fly model, we weren't able to sort of confirm any kind of a clear peak in the integrated information using a different time scale. So it's still something that I'm very interested in looking, but still not clear whether this is the case. I don't know if Hayato has some idea or insight into the appropriate time scale for consciousness or something from the physics point of view.

1:12:53 *Hayato*: Yeah, I have some thoughts, but maybe it becomes a long story, so, and also connects to the observer dependence problem. So I was thinking about how to explain these very important things in one thread, and I found that first, the very simple fact that there comes no identically-same two events. Every event is different in some respect. But to do science, or more generally, some recognition of law, we need some criterion of sameness. For example, you want to know how to heal the disease? You should identify the different persons, people as the same kind of samples or something. Of course, there is no identical persons, but you have to identify in the members of the same group something. So all the scientific studies depend on some choice of the sameness. And so in that sense, all the science depends on this kind of choice of the sameness as you both pointed out and I think that there is no canonical choice of the sameness. You can choose sameness. But if you choose some sameness, then you can talk about observables. Observables means some kind of quantities. You can observe something, maybe it randomly change the value or no value like a quantum case. But by measuring process it become half the value or something. There may be indefinite nature of such kind of quantities, but anyway we can imagine that the quantities has some kind of structure between the quantities. So in mathematical terms it will be some algebra of the observables. Then how to connect this idea, theoretical idea to the experimental thing, is the key is expectation value. So theory provides expectation value of something and we can connect theory and experiments by comparing the theoretical expectation value and the average of samples. So all the quantitative science depends on this

structure like algebra, observables, and some mapping from the observables algebra to some number system. So this is called a state in mathematics and algebra. And state is something like the mapping of quantities of random variables or observables into its expectation value. So this mapping of expectation is technically called state. So if you start from observer algebra and state, this is a starting point of noncommutative probability theory. That is if this algebra is commutative, then the conventional probability theory can reconstruct from this commutative algebra and state. But if this is noncommutative as Nao pointed out, if the process is essential, then these algebra should be noncommutative. Then we have the noncommutativity probability space features which I call intuitively the quantum mathematics or something. So in this case the observable dependence is described. The other kind of observable dependence can be described because you can't have the classical probability space for all the observable. But if you choose one observable, one observable like position or momentum, you can choose this. Then you can construct the classical probability space. So the choice of context or the choice of measuring something is by choosing something. So context you can have the classical kind of reality. So this kind of observer with dependence is well formulated by using noncommutative probability space. So I think this multilayered observable observer dependence can be described by using noncommutative probability. And the last thing I would say is the connection of the category theory and noncommutativity probability. Very interestingly, if the category is given like a causal system -- causal system give us some category. Like a causation is arrow, and the composition is A is cause of B, B causes C. Then indirectly of course at least the A causes C or something, so it becomes can be considered as a category. There is many kind of category. But if the category is given, then the algebra reflecting this categorical structure is necessarily noncommutative if there is a nontrivial arrow between two objects. So actually the category theory and the noncommutative probability is from the mathematical point of view, it's kind of the two aspects of the same thing, like the fundamental observer dependence or contextual dependence or something. And this contextuality, like in topos theory, actually, this choosing concepts and the transformation between the contexts can be formulated in terms of topos, which is a very powerful kind of category. So sorry for the too-long explanation! But without that, this very fundamental question cannot be organized. Sorry for the long explanation.

1:20:48 *Daniel*: Oh, it's it's awesome. I mean, empirically, if you have a sensor that's getting measurements at a certain time scale, then there's a binding of the timescale of the observer and the processing. Can I ask a question from the chat? All right. Dave asks. At one time, Professor Tononi was representing the shape of the relations between complexity and consciousness, such that too-richly-connected systems are nonconscious. They're overwhelmed by the complexity. Recently, the inverted U that shows this relation seems to have become scarce, leading to undue confusion. Have IIT people abandoned the idea that there is a bounded sweet zone for consciousness? Can a system be either too simple or too complex to act consciously? So does IIT lead us to a kind of monotonic consciousness concept, or could there be a U shaped relationship with information integration and qualia?

1:22:07 *Nao*: I see. Yeah. I can also see that comment here. In the end, the question is, can the system be either too simple or too complex to act consciously?

1:22:37 *Daniel*: Yeah.

1:22:38 *Nao*: In the sense yeah, from an IIT point of view, there are several things that needs to be said, but inverted U is still there in a sense. And here this person seems to be confusing between the axis of the kind of complexity and the axis of the connectedness. In IIT original formulation - and it's still true for the IIT 4.0, which is the latest one - when the system is too connected, let's say if you have hundred neurons and each of them are connected to everybody in a uniform way, then IIT predicts that it doesn't have much complexity or compositionality or uniqueness to arrive from that kind of system. And even if you cut the system, it doesn't matter much. And so that would lead to, most likely, very low level of consciousness. I think that's what... [Reads viewer's note] Yes. I should have typed "connectivity." Yes. If that's the case, that's fine.

1:24:08 *Daniel*: But higher complexity, which is granted by some small world or some sparse connectivity structure, higher complexity is monotonically associated with more consciousness?

1:24:23 *Nao*: That's not the case in IIT, and that is true from the beginning. And the easiest kind of example is to have a two highly complex kind of system that is loosely connected between them. It's a kind of a situation where you are interested right, in a sense like ant colony, each ant has a huge brain. Even though it looks extremely small, the number of the neurons they have is more than one million, right?

1:24:54 *Daniel*: In that order, yes. Around a million.

1:24:57 *Nao*: Yeah. So IIT would naturally predict that the causal connection or integrated information arising from this 1 million neurons within the ant are going to be really massive. It's very difficult to disconnect in any way, in any meaningful way. However, interaction between a single ant to the another ant has a much less direct causal relationship. And therefore the local minima or local maxima of the Phi value is going to be very huge within each ant. But when you combine or when you treat all these lots of ants, it definitely does bring some kind of intelligent and complex kind of behavior. But phenomenality is not there at that level. Phenomenality, consciousness, lives within this maximum level of integrated information, pretty much like what we talked about in timescale stuff. We have a huge, complex and very intelligent kind of behavior and artifacts in the long time scale and also short time scale. But what matters for our phenomenology is this particular several orders of 100 milliseconds that corresponds the maximum of the integrated information.

1:26:26 *Daniel*: So you still have emergent intelligence at the colony level, but that doesn't necessarily mean that you have qualia arising at that level for analogous reasons why our qualia are at the spiking timescale despite that being only one of the nested timescales.

1:26:47 *Nao*: Exactly.

1:26:49 *Daniel*: Very cool.

1:26:50 *Nao*: IIT predicts that the intelligence and the consciousness – qualia - is completely dissociable. And that leads to the commentary about large language model, probably, right. Large language model is probably structurally built to be very simple, almost like probably cerebellum in the human brain, which accounts roughly like 80% of our neurons in the brain. Out of ten to the eleven neurons in the brain, 80% are in the cerebellum. But even if you remove it or lose it or are born without it, it seems consciousness is not that different. And the simple kind of prediction that cerebellum is

doing, maybe something similar to the large neural[?] model is doing. It's very modular, it's parallel, it's not integrated, does a lot of intelligent things, but nothing to do with the consciousness.

1:28:00 *Daniel*: Very interesting! Well, maybe in our closing sections, of course, anything you want to share or ask, but how does active inference benefit and grow from what you're sharing? And how do you see things unfolding for people interested in these topics?

1:28:30 *Nao*: Do you want to say something first?

1:28:32 *Hayato*: Yeah, I'm thinking, "How would we know?"

1:28:35 *Nao*: Okay, then from my end I used to have difficulty in thinking about active inference or Markov blanket and things like that. But by broadening my perspective and so becoming more generous, I started to feel like maybe some aspects of the thinking and also formulation can be relevant at least for the explanation of the biological systems in various domain. And if it's also useful to explain intelligence or construct intelligence, that would be great. And from our work of the quantum qualia of hypothesis, if qualia is something that is influenced by its measurement, then that aspect may be emphasizing this - Usually qualia of consciousness is kind of considered a passive construct. Like at a given moment what I'm experiencing, static, passive. But now I'm more thinking about because of this collaboration with the other people. That can be the case. And it's more to do with the process. And the process it may not be the kind of the level of the active inference that you are thinking like not the level of the acting on the world, but more to do with this state itself, influencing itself might be some kind of important insight to understand the qualia.

1:30:24 *Hayato*: Okay, my comment is - it is related to the concept of states again, because expectation value I pointed out the importance of expectation value. But for example what is the expectation value for example the strength of causality or something? Then the problem of time scale is very important. So you can cause grain for example the brain activity for one time, scale another timescale. So I think if IIT is correct there is a good timescale which is of importance great importance of choosing this structure. Then I think the brain information or something causal structure should be the good category and you can construct a noncommutative algebra and the state is defined or something. So the timescale is quite fundamental. And on the other hand the state on the category that is state on the category algebra can be represented by some kind of weight on arrows, the positive kind of weight on arrows. So the changing the state is the change in the weight of these arrows. The positive definite function. I think the transition or the weighting of this arrow is very at least mathematically very interesting to compare the active inference as a mathematical point of view. So good weight, to the better weight, or something is very how to say interesting to compare. I don't have much knowledge about active inference but it seems to me it is quite useful to connect this level the state change or something. So yeah it is very interesting for me. And other thing, is I forgot the third point, but yeah so yeah yes, as now already okay point out I talked about measurements instruments but the point of this notion is probe system. So measurement is always often considered as a very direct kind of interaction like the system and the environment. But environment has some kind of probe into the system then the interaction is occurred with this probe and this system. I think it is very analogous to the qualia the case of - so of course the outer world is relating to the brain inside of course at least process, or the historical or developmental. But I think through perception or something the brain has its probe over the world.

For example this interaction is very hard to say, interesting. So measurement, the analogy to the measurement theory may be some physically within the brain, but some kind of probe of the outer system under this qualia is interacting. So I think it unifies picture, I think. What do you think now, for example?

1:34:51 *Nao*: Yeah, that's actually very much related to what I was actually constructing this morning.

1:35:01 *Nao*: Yeah.

1:35:01 *Nao*: So I was reading this Ozawa paper that describes the instrument, and I'm getting better understanding what it means. But what he says is that every observable A of a system S is identified with the observable A tensor with the instrument I over system S plus S prime. So S here is the original system, and S prime is the one that with any system external to S . And what Hayato was meaning is that this S prime is probe system, which is a part of the environment. Right?

1:35:50 *Hayato*: Yeah.

1:35:51 *Nao*: And so here what this quantum, in this case, quantum kind of system description. But it's also true for the quantum cognition. And in my case, it is also true for the quantum qualia hypothesis, is that some kind of qualia experiencing system is interacting with the world, but through the sort of membrane, or sort of that like a Markov blanket like thing is already filtering interaction as a sensory input and out tension. And this part itself is kind of interacting with itself. These arrows are the critical part. And then if we translate that other way to in our case, this correspond to every qualia of a qualia-experiencing system S , which is, in the case of IIT, it's called a complex observer, a times instrument of a system s prime, S prime. And this S prime here, I think, will include all the neuronal processes that support the underlying qualia, but it doesn't really necessarily directly include the external environment. Many people start to do that, but if you do that, then suddenly hallucination or dreaming and things like that becomes very difficult to explain, including too much. I think that corresponds to what you wanted to say, right?

1:37:30 *Hayato*: Yes, exactly.

1:37:33 *Nao*: Yeah.

1:37:35 *Daniel*: Well, this is really awesome. I very much appreciate that we could have this conversation. Is there anything else you want to add or ask?

1:37:46 *Nao*: Thank you. I also enjoyed and it was also good for me to formulate my thoughts as well.

1:37:53 *Hayato*: Yeah, I'm very surprised. Yeah, surprised me. The how consistent our thoughts are. It was just a surprise for me, maybe. The conversation often goes, how to say, to diverge. But our conversation has a very surprisingly convergence. So I think it's quite interesting in itself. I learned much from this conversation. Thank you for inviting us.

1:38:43 *Daniel*: Thank you so much. Hope to join on your channel and hear updates on your research as things develop. So thank you again.

1:38:53 *Hayato*: Thank you.

1:38:54 *Nao*: Thank you.

1:38:55 *Hayato*: Bye.

1:38:56 *Nao*: Bye.

1:38:57 *Hayato*: Bye.